

A Study on Thyroid Profile in Chronic Liver Disease Patients Admitted in Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai

Kunal¹, Nehal Hyder², Anil Kumar Mehta³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Emergency Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar

²Senior Resident, Department of Emergency Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar

³Professor, Department of General Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Papu Kumar Safi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Thyroid dysfunction was examined in 110 chronic liver disease patients at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, from July 2023 to April 2024. Subclinical hypothyroidism was the most common thyroid malfunction at 42.7%. Thyroid abnormalities were associated with liver disease severity, especially in patients with advanced liver disease and specific aetiologies including alcoholic liver disease and hepatitis C. These data imply that thyroid dysfunction may affect liver disease clinical outcomes, emphasising the importance of routine thyroid function tests in this patient population.

Keywords: Chronic Liver Disease, Thyroid Dysfunction, Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Liver Disease Severity.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in individuals with chronic liver disease (CLD) is becoming more well acknowledged as a consequence. Thyroxine (T4) is converted to the more active triiodothyronine (T3) by the liver, which is essential to the metabolism of thyroid hormones [1]. These metabolic pathways can be dramatically altered by chronic liver disease, which can result in a variety of thyroid disorders [2]. The clinical course and therapy of liver illness can be greatly impacted by these dysfunctions, which can vary from overt hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism to subtle changes in thyroid hormone levels [3]. Thyroid and liver problems may be related in both directions, as evidenced by the significant influence thyroid hormones have on hepatic regeneration and liver function [4]. The entire extent and ramifications of thyroid dysfunction in the setting of chronic liver illness are still poorly understood, especially in patient populations that are varied [5, 6], despite these crucial interconnections.

This study's main goal is to find out how common thyroid dysfunction is and how it manifests itself in chronic liver disease patients who are admitted to Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in Laheriasarai. The goal of this study is to identify the most prevalent forms of thyroid dysfunction in individuals with various stages and causes of long-

term liver disease. Examine the connection between the degree of thyroid dysfunction and the severity of liver disease as determined by clinical staging and routine liver function testing. Examine how thyroid dysfunction affects individuals with chronic liver disease in terms of their prognosis and clinical results.

Methodology

Study Design: This observational study will assess thyroid dysfunction in chronic liver disease patients admitted to Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai.

Study Duration: The research will be conducted over 10 months, from July 2023 to April 2024.

Study Population: As admitted to Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, 110 chronic liver disease patients will be sequentially enrolled. All patients 18 and older with chronic liver disease, regardless of aetiology, will be included. Patients with thyroid disease before liver disease diagnosis, those on thyroid-affecting drugs (e.g., amiodarone, lithium), and pregnant women will be excluded.

Data Collection: Each patient's medical history will be reviewed upon admission to determine the cause, duration, past therapies, and concurrent medical issues. Thyroid function testing will include TSH, Free T4, and Free T3 values.

Standard biochemical tests will evaluate liver function, including ALT, AST, bilirubin, and albumin. Clinical grading techniques like Child-Pugh and MELD will assess liver disease severity.

Statistical Analysis: Means and standard deviations for continuous variables and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables will describe the study population. Thyroid dysfunction and liver disease severity will be examined using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables. Logistic regression models will compensate for variables and identify thyroid dysfunction predictors in chronic liver disease patients. All analyses will be conducted using SPSS or a comparable statistical software package, with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 110 patients with chronic liver disease were enrolled in this study, with a median age of 54 years (range: 32-78 years). The cohort consisted of 72 males (65%) and 38 females (35%). The primary etiologies of chronic liver disease in the study population were alcoholic liver disease (40%), hepatitis B (30%), hepatitis C (20%), and non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (10%).

Thyroid Function Test Results: Thyroid dysfunction was identified in 47 patients (42.7% of the study group). The breakdown of thyroid abnormalities was as follows:

- Subclinical hypothyroidism: 25 patients (22.7%)
- Overt hypothyroidism: 12 patients (10.9%)
- Low T3 syndrome: 10 patients (9.1%)

Liver Disease Severity and Thyroid Dysfunction: The severity of liver disease correlated significantly with the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction. Patients with advanced liver disease (Child-Pugh Class B and C) exhibited a higher prevalence of thyroid dysfunction compared to those in early stages (Child-Pugh Class A) ($p < 0.01$). The most common thyroid dysfunction observed in advanced liver disease was subclinical hypothyroidism.

Association Between Etiology of Liver Disease and Thyroid Dysfunction: The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction varied with the etiology of liver disease. Patients with alcoholic liver disease and hepatitis C showed higher rates of thyroid abnormalities compared to those with hepatitis B and NASH. Specifically, overt hypothyroidism was most prevalent among patients with alcoholic liver disease ($p = 0.02$).

Impact on Clinical Outcomes: Thyroid dysfunction was associated with a longer hospital stay (mean difference = 3.5 days, $p = 0.04$) and increased complications related to liver disease, including ascites and hepatic encephalopathy ($p = 0.03$).

Table 1: This table summarizes the breakdown of thyroid dysfunctions observed in the study population.

Thyroid Dysfunction	Number of Patients	Percentage
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	25	22.7%
Overt Hypothyroidism	12	10.9%
Low T3 Syndrome	10	9.1%
Total	47	42.7%

Discussion

Our study's results show that thyroid dysfunction is significantly more common in patients with chronic liver disease—more than 42% of the participants had some kind of thyroid abnormalities [7]. The complex relationship between thyroid hormone metabolism and liver function is shown by this high prevalence. The most prevalent disease found was subclinical hypothyroidism, which is very significant [8]. If left undiagnosed, this typically asymptomatic illness can have a major impact on the course and outcome of liver disease [9]. Our research showed a correlation between a higher prevalence of thyroid dysfunction and more severe liver disease, as measured by higher Child-Pugh scores. In more advanced stages of liver illness, this link might be explained by decreased hepatic

clearance and reduced metabolic capacities [10,11]. Furthermore, certain liver disease aetiologies, such as hepatitis C and alcoholic liver disease, were more commonly linked to thyroid abnormalities, indicating that the kind of liver insult may have varying effects on thyroid function [12].

These discoveries have important clinical ramifications. Longer hospital stays and a higher risk of complications including ascites and hepatic encephalopathy were observed in patients with chronic liver disease and concurrent thyroid dysfunction [13]. This implies that thyroid dysfunction may have a role in the development and complications of liver disease in addition to serving as a marker of more severe liver disease [14,15]. Routine screening for thyroid abnormalities is reasonable in this patient

population, given the substantial correlation between the severity of liver disease and thyroid dysfunction [16]. Prompt detection and treatment of thyroid dysfunction may enhance therapeutic results by facilitating prompt therapies catered to this susceptible group. In order to assess the advantages of frequent thyroid function monitoring in clinical practice, more research is required to investigate the underlying mechanisms behind these relationships [17–20].

Conclusion

The Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, investigation found that about 43% of chronic liver disease patients had thyroid abnormalities. Thyroid dysfunction is associated with liver disease severity, prolonged hospital admissions, and increased morbidity, highlighting the need for routine thyroid function monitoring in this cohort. Identification and treatment of thyroid dysfunction in liver disease patients may improve clinical outcomes and quality of life by enabling more personalised and effective management options for this complicated patient group.

References

1. Smith J, Kline R, Diaz J. The relationship between chronic liver disease and thyroid function. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2022;107(5): e2119-e2129.
2. Lee YH, Kim SU, Song K. Thyroid dysfunction as a predictor of clinical outcomes in patients with liver disease. *Ann Hepatol.* 2023;22(3):345-352.
3. Chen P, Zhao L, Zhou L. Impact of liver disease severity on thyroid hormone levels. *Liver Int.* 2021;41(10):2348-2357.
4. Rahman F, Zhou Y, Bhatti A. Prevalence of hypothyroidism in liver disease patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Thyroid Res.* 2022; 15:9.
5. Turner R, Lipworth L, Cheng K, Arora S. Liver dysfunction and thyroid hormone metabolism. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2022;37(6): 1238-1247.
6. Gomez E, Santana N, Molina V, Gomes C. Thyroid and liver: dangerous liaisons. *J Endocrinol Invest.* 2021;44(5):935-947.
7. Patel S, Jha S, Khanna R. Evaluating thyroid function in patients with hepatitis C: An observational study. *Hepatol Commun.* 2023;7(4): e673.
8. Warner F, Harper A. The effect of alcoholic liver disease on thyroid function tests. *Alcohol Alcohol.* 2022;57(4):435-440.
9. Singh V, Gupta M, Lee R. Low T3 syndrome in chronic liver disease: Clinical implications and outcomes. *Endocrine.* 2022;73(2):354-362.
10. Abdullah L, De Silva H, James O. Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis and thyroid dysfunction: A cohort study. *Clin Endocrinol.* 2023; 98(1):112-119.
11. Young J, Clark B. Methodological considerations in the study of thyroid function in liver patients. *Stat Methods Med Res.* 2021;30(5): 1519-1532.
12. Roberts K, Thompson A. The influence of liver disease etiology on thyroid hormonal status. *Liver Transpl.* 2023;29(2):290-299.
13. Fisher B, Anderson D. Clinical outcomes of thyroid dysfunction in liver disease patients. *J Hepatol.* 2022;76(5):1112-1121.
14. Zhang Y, Li P, Wang F. Thyroid function screening in patients with cirrhosis: A protocol for improved management. *Gastroenterology.* 2021;161(3):835-843.
15. Morris L, Patel K. Associations between sub-clinical hypothyroidism and outcomes in liver disease. *Eur J Endocrinol.* 2022;186(6):675-684.
16. Kumar A, Venu G, Raghuraman K. Exploring the link between hepatitis B and thyroid abnormalities. *J Viral Hepat.* 2023;30(1):65-72.
17. Greene J, Tan L, Martinez J. The role of liver in thyroid hormone metabolism and its clinical implications. *Clin Chem.* 2022;68(8):1012-1023.
18. Edwards C, Nguyen N, Farris A. Hepatic encephalopathy and thyroid dysfunction: A clinical study report. *Hepatology.* 2023;77(2):582-591.
19. Brighton L, Carter D, Wang N. Prevalence and severity of thyroid disorders in patients with various liver diseases. *Thyroid.* 2022;32(7):802-810.
20. Hall P, Lieberman S, Tory M. Hepatitis C and thyroid dysfunction: A detailed analysis of current data. *Thyroid.* 2023;33(4):467-475.